

More lessons from migraine

T Whitmarsh^{1*}

¹*Glasgow Homoeopathic Hospital, Glasgow, UK*

It is very pleasing to publish another double-blind placebo-controlled study of homeopathic prophylaxis of migraine (this issue). This study has been referred to in the original Norwegian¹ on a number of occasions by myself and others when trying to assess the other randomised controlled trials in this area,^{2,3} but has not so far been available in English. There is now the opportunity for everyone to compare the results of three well performed studies, all using the same diagnostic criteria, those of the International Headache Society.⁴

This is an unusual situation in homeopathic research, which has had a history of multiple small trials in unrelated areas. In a previous editorial,⁵ I discussed the question of reproducibility of results of trials, prompted by the comments of Linde in his meta-analysis.⁶ I concluded that on the face of it, there looked to have been some replication with the studies of Walach and Whitmarsh, leading to a reproducible conclusion that homeopathy is not effective in chronic headache, but that this did not stand up to closer examination given the variability in trial population and design. Many questions were raised about future trial design if further studies were to be attempted of homeopathy in migraine. The latest study answers few of these, but I think it can contribute to the broadening debate about the kind of studies we would need in order to show the effectiveness that most practitioners undoubtedly feel homeopathy has in migraine, or any other disorder.

Straumsheim and colleagues studied 73 patients, of whom 68 completed the study, randomised to individualised homeopathic treatment (any remedy, 35 patients) or identical placebo (33 patients). They used a baseline run-in month to record clinical data and then treated for 4 months (any dosage regime) with monthly assessments, using daily diary cards as the basis for measuring migraine attack frequency, intensity and analgesic consumption.

This methodology is very similar to that of the trial of Whitmarsh *et al* although he was limited to a choice of 11 remedies. Results from diary card analysis show a reduction of about 30% in migraine frequency across the time of the trial with no sig-

nificant difference between groups. Results are similar for mean pain intensity and analgesic consumption. More interestingly, the patients were diagnosed and suggested for entry into the trial by an otherwise uninvolved neurologist, who made a blinded independent assessment of the outcome measures with the patient at the end of the trial. This assessment showed a significant difference in attack frequency per month in favour of the active homeopathy group ($P = 0.04$) and so the authors are justified in their conclusion that homeopathy was not shown to be inactive in this situation by all measures.

The authors make a number of very pertinent points about factors which contribute towards the difficulty in drawing conclusions from their study. It is interesting to note the specific collection of data about possible initial aggravations after the first homeopathic treatment. There is quite a high reporting of worsening of symptoms initially in both active and placebo groups. They comment in the discussion that specific advice was given to reduce analgesic consumption, in particular ergotamine use. As they point out, ergotamine withdrawal is associated with a worsening of headache and the apparent high use of ergotamine preparations in the Norwegian migraine population at the time of the study may well be the most relevant factor here. Ergotamine withdrawal headache (and incidentally ergotamine overuse headache) can be strikingly similar to migraine. They did, however, perform a sub-group analysis excluding the most frequent ergotamine users, which showed no significant difference between active and placebo.

Another factor making assessment difficult is the question of selection of patients for entry. Straumsheim's patients were selected after an advertisement about the study. This of course biases the study population towards those with enthusiasm for homeopathy or those with chronic, difficult to manage migraine who feel they have tried everything else. The two other studies using IHS criteria also inevitably had biased entry groups. Whitmarsh's study involved patients in a specialist migraine clinic (only about 1% of migraine patients will get to such a clinic in Britain) and so were inevitably a difficult group to manage. Walach's patients had a median headache duration of 23 years, another real challenge. Other

*Correspondence: Dr Tom Whitmarsh, Glasgow Homoeopathic Hospital, 1053 Great Western Road, Glasgow, G12 0XQ, UK.

exclusion criteria in the current study were patients using stimulants (presumably caffeine or maybe alcohol) and those on regular medication of various sorts, including hormonal preparations. This of course excludes the largest group of migraine sufferers, young women liable to be taking oral contraceptives. None of the studies are really studying 'typical patients' and all are looking at groups hard to treat by any standards.

Despite all these problems, migraine and chronic headache is now one of the clinical areas in which trials of homeopathy have been most often reported. None of them has shown strong effects over placebo on the outcome measures used, but only that of Walach was convincingly negative in all respects. Straumsheim's study is more evidence, if it were needed, of just how difficult it is to perform placebo-controlled trials in homeopathy. The really interesting thing from this study is the difference between the neurologist's patient-led assessment of effect and the straight data from diary cards. The emerging importance of quality of life measurements as probably a much better way of quantifying the benefits of homeopathy is a development reflected in more recent trials of conventional drug therapy in migraine and many other areas. I see the 'Neurologist's assessment' as a first attempt at getting at quantifying some of this quality of life improvement which is a frequent report from patients under homeopathic treatment. This adds to an analysis of the subsidiary outcome of patient's global assessment on data from Whitmarsh's trial (not reported in the original paper), which was recently performed as part of a meta-analysis of trials of individualised homeopathy.⁷ This report of patient's own assessment of effect significantly favours the active homeopathy group at the end of the trial.

If future randomised controlled trials are to be done in migraine with homeopathy, quality of life assessment is going to be very important. This was, incidentally, the strong message taken home in all clinical

areas from the recent RLHH conference on Improving the Success of Homeopathy.⁸ In this current study there are suggestive hints of an effect which supports the clinical impressions of efficacy in migraine. This raises the question of whether there is any more mileage in double-blind randomised placebo trials. The history of trials of homeopathy in migraine gives some of the strongest evidence that well performed outcome or audit prospective studies are likely to be more useful in the long run in the promotion of homeopathy and the objectification of our clinical impressions.

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